

The Effect of a Nurse-Driven Protocol on the Incidence of Aspiration Pneumonia in a Tertiary Healthcare System

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Background

Aspiration pneumonia (AP) is a type of pneumonia that is often diagnosed in the elderly. It is caused by the introduction of pathogenic bacteria from the oral-pharyngeal cavity, or the gastrointestinal tract, into the lungs. These events lead to extended hospitalization and poor patient outcomes. 80% of pneumonia diagnoses are related to aspirations and is the leading cause of death with patients diagnosed with pneumonia.

Purpose

Develop a comprehensive aspiration pneumonia nurse-driven protocol (APNP) to reduce the incidence of AP in patients admitted to the medical-surgical units and critical care unit at a major Veterans Administration Hospital.

Methods

Population

- Acutely ill veterans admitted to critical care, medical/surgical units, and acute spinal cord injury units (N = 134)
- Exclusion Criteria: Patients admitted to the project units with an existing AP diagnosis

Design

- Interventional study that utilized the PDSA Model for Process Improvement and focused on the development and piloting of the APNP

Measuring Instruments

- AP Verification Checklist
- Patient Demographic Data Tool
- Nurse Level of Knowledge
- APNP Checklist

Intervention

- APNP designed by facility staff for use with patients who met inclusion criteria

Framework: PDSA Model for Quality Improvement

Scenario: At a large healthcare system in Southern California, facility leadership seek to lower the prevalence of aspiration pneumonia (AP) cases in five acute care settings. Current condition: Ninety percent of pneumonia diagnoses are AP.

Act: Plan the next rapid cycle; determine if change can be implemented and sustained.

Plan: Define objectives, questions, who, what, when, where and plan data collection.

Study: Complete the analysis of the data and compare to expected outcomes and insights.

Do: Carry out the plan and collect the data. Begin analysis of the data.

Results

Hospital-Acquired AP Diagnoses November - March

Hospital-Acquired AP Diagnoses November - March Pre-and-Post Intervention

Group	Months (N)	Mean (SD)	t-value	p-value
Pre-Intervention	5	1.49 (+/- 1.3)	1.41	0.23
Post-Intervention	5	0.4 (+/- 0.5)		

Discussion

A didactic and hands-on educational intervention improved nurses' knowledge of AP.

Targeted intervention with patient populations at risk for acquiring AP during their hospitalization is a key factor in prevention.

The finding of a decreased incidence of AP was consistent with multiple research studies noted in the review of the literature.

Future Implications

Nursing staff play a critical role in monitoring and prevention of AP.

Nurses need to be knowledgeable of AP and commit to meticulous implementation of the APNP.

AP nurse level of knowledge and training suggests nurses have a heightened sense of autonomy within their practice.

The reduction in the cases of AP could lead to decreases in lengths of stay, thus, avoiding unnecessary hospitalization costs.

Conclusions and Recommendations

AP is a preventable medical condition. Nurses' level of knowledge, their training, and meticulous commitment to following the steps of the AP prevention protocol were major factors that resulted in a clinically significant reduction in the incidence of AP. A larger sample size of patients placed on the APNP over a longer period of time, would allow for more rigor and reliability of interventions and patient outcomes. Further dissemination to other sites of care is also needed for generalizability.